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A Study on Customer Retention With Reference to Kottha's Foods, Kadapa

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Abstract:

Customer retention is a business's ability to keep existing customers and continue to generate revenue from them. Companies use different tactics to convert first-time buyers into repeat shoppers. In other words, customer retention allows a business to increase the profitability of an existing customer and maximize their lifetime value (LTV).

Customer retention is a process where a business aims to convince existing customers to keep purchasing its products or services. Since a customer has already made a purchase, it's different from lead generation, which is the effort involved in capturing contact information of businesses or individuals who are likely to buy a product or service.

Instead, customer retention is focused on existing customers. The goal is to increase repeat purchases by building customer loyalty through excellent customer service, product value, and a distinct advantage over similar products or services.

Customer retention requires a series of initiatives and processes designed to build trust and enhance customer loyalty. It helps structure the fulfillment of brand promises through the consistent delivery of value.

Keywords: Customer retention rate, churn, lifetime value, loyalty programs, net promoter score.

1. Introduction

A customer is someone who buys products or services. In sales, commerce, and economics, a customer (sometimes known as a client, buyer, or purchaser) is the recipient of a good, service, product, or an idea, obtained from a seller, vendor, or supplier via a financial transaction or an exchange for money or some other valuable consideration. Retention is the ability to keep or continue having something.

2. Literature Review

Kotler P., Keller K.L. (2006): Measuring customer satisfaction and the factors responsible. It is one of the important activities for any firm. It has been stated that the highly satisfied customer stays loyal and longer, buys more products repeatedly,

and gives less attention to The competitor brand is less sensitive to price.

Kumar et al. (2009): Mentioned that "high quality of service will result in high customer Satisfaction and will result it into increases in customer loyalty. In the study, it is observed that there are four major factors: tangibility, reliability, convenience, and competence. These all have Substantial differences between expectations and perceptions, with tangibility having the smallest gap and convenience having the largest gap.

Mohd. J. et al. (2015): Researcher throws light on the importance of customer satisfaction in any industry. Good quality service and improved customer satisfaction will lead to enhance the number of customers. Good service providers can also save the money required for different promotions and marketing activities, as satisfied customers will always endorse these brands.

Chandra U., et al. (2016): Here focus on opportunities and Challenges of the Indian Pharmaceutical Sector. The Indian pharmaceutical sector is expected to grow with a faster compound annual growth rate (CAGR) compared to the global growth rate during the period 2015- 2020.

3. Industry Profile

The retail industry in India has been a cornerstone of its economic development, showcasing remarkable growth and evolution over the years. As one of the world’s fastest-growing retail markets, India’s retail sector is characterized by a unique blend of traditional formats and modern retailing concepts. This dynamic mix is powered by a growing economy, urbanization, and an increasingly affluent middle class.

Retail is the sale of goods or services directly to the end-user for consumption. Retail comprises the final step in the supply chain, and hence plays the important role of disseminating the finished products to the actual consumers.

4. Company Profile

Kottha’s Foods– Kadapa Branch

Kottha’s Foods (often branded as Kotthas or Kottha’s Ganesh) is a well-established food manufacturing company based in Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, known for its traditional masala powders, spices, and pickles. Founded by Mr. Kottha Naga Kumar, the company started as a small, homemade "rasam powder" business in 1983 and has grown over four decades into a prominent local brand.

- **Founder:** Mr. Kottha Naga Kumar
- **CEO:** Kotthas Naga Abhiram
- **Location:** Vinayaka Nagar, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh
- **Established:** 1983 (branded "Kottha’s Foods" in 2000)
- **Specialization:** Authentic Andhra-style masalas, spice powders, instant mixes, and pickles
- **Products:**
 - Kottha’s Foods offers a wide range of products tailored to traditional culinary needs, including
 - **Masala Powders:** Chicken Masala, Ganesh Rasam Powder, Sambar Powder, and various curry powders.
 - **Spices & Flours:** Red Chilli Powder, Turmeric Powder, and various flours
 - **Pickles:** Various Andhra-style pickles
 - **Others:** Instant mixes and sweets

5. Statement of the Problem

In today’s competitive business landscape, acquiring new customers is significantly more expensive than retaining existing ones. However, many companies struggle with customer churn due to a lack of effective retention strategies. Despite efforts in marketing, businesses often face challenges in understanding customer behaviors, identifying the key factors influencing loyalty, and implementing personalized engagement strategies.

5.1. Need of the Study

Customer retention is crucial for businesses as it directly impacts profitability, brand reputation, and long-term sustainability. Understanding customer retention helps businesses develop strategies to keep existing customers engaged and satisfied, leading to higher revenue and lower acquisition costs.

5.2. Objectives of the Study

- To know the demographic profile of respondents
- To study the factors which are affecting for retaining of customers
- To study the different measurements of retention metrics
- To study the customer lifetime value

5.3. Scope of the Study

It is one of the best strategies for businesses to increase their revenue growth, and it also aims to maintain long-term relationships with customers and increase customer lifetime value. It also enhances brand reputation and competitive positioning and is helpful for long-term success.

- **Primary Data:** It is data that is collected by questionnaire and observation
- **Research Design:** A descriptive research design is used for the present study.
- **Descriptive Research:** Descriptive analysis is the process of summarizing and interpreting raw data to uncover patterns, trends, and key characteristics
- **Population:** Population refers to the group of individuals, objects, or events that a researcher is interested in studying and generating findings. The Population is 200
- **Sampling Techniques:** Convenience Sampling
- **Sample Size:** The sample size consists of 120 respondents.

Formula of percentage analysis:

$$\frac{\text{No of respondents}}{\text{Total No of Respondents}} \times 100 \tag{1}$$

5.4. Limitations of the Study

- As the time given for the completion of the project is limited
- The survey is limited to only Kadapa
- It is difficult to collect more accurate data from the customers.

6. Data Analysis

Table 1: Employee Status

Employment Status	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Full-time Employee	55	45.80%
Part-time Employee	25	20.80%
Unemployed	20	16.70%
Self-employed	20	16.70%
Total	120	100%

Figure 1: Employee Status.

From the above graph 4.4, it is inferred that 41.67% of the respondents are full-time employees, 25% of the respondents are part-time, 20.83% of the respondents are unemployed, & 12.50% are self-employed.

Table 2: Monthly income

Income (in Rs)	Respondents	Percentage (%)
20,000-30,000	40	33.30%
30,000-40,000	50	41.70%
40,000-50,000	30	25.00%
Total	120	100%

Figure 2: Monthly income.

From the above graph 4.5, it is inferred that 33.30% of the respondents get income between 20,000-30,000, 41.70% get income between 30,000-40,000, and 25% of the get income between 40,000-50,000.

Table 3: Satisfaction with customer service

Response	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	92	76.7%
No	28	23.3%
Total	120	100%

Figure 3: Satisfaction with customer service.

From the above graph 4.11, it is inferred that 65% of respondents were members of customer loyalty programs and 35% of respondents were not members of customer loyalty programs

Table 4: prefer to be contacted for promotions or updates

Option	Respondents	Percentage (%)
E-mails	48	40%
calls	18	15%
sms	36	30%
Social media	18	15%
Total	120	100%

Figure 4: prefer to be contacted for promotions or updates.

A large portion of respondents 40% prefer receiving promotions through the mail, and the next most of respondents prefer SMS, with 36%, and the next preferred is through social media and calls, with the 15%

7. Findings

- It is found that most of the respondents are between 18 and 28 years.
- It is found that the majority of the respondents are male.
- It is found that half of the respondents are married.
- The majority of the respondents are full-time employees.
- It is found that the majority of respondents are with income of 30k to 40k.
- It is found 40.00% respondents will shop often in retail stores.
- It is found that 45% of respondents are satisfied with the product quality offered by the company
- It is found that 31.7% of respondents chose product quality as a factor to have a repeat purchase
- The majority of the respondents are satisfied with the customer service
- It is found that most of the respondents are occasionally retained by the same store
- The majority of the respondents are members of the customer loyalty or reward programs
- 30% of the respondents have been shopping with the store for 1-2 years.
- The majority of the respondents will recommend the store to their friends and family members.
- The majority of the respondents are very satisfied with the shopping experience.
- 30% of respondents feel somewhat easy to find the product that they need to purchase

- It is found that the majority of the respondents buy groceries
- The majority of the respondents wait for a discount/on sale at the shop.
- The majority of respondents are likely trying new products
- It is found that the majority of respondents prefer to be contacted for promotions and updates via email
- It is found that the majority of respondents have stopped shopping at a store due to poor service

the key factors influencing customer loyalty. The company has a strong customer base with good satisfaction levels and repeat customers. However, issues like poor service experiences have led to customer loss in some cases. By focusing on improving customer service, maintaining product quality, and offering attractive promotions, Kottha's Foods can enhance customer satisfaction and retention. Strengthening relationships with customers and adopting effective retention strategies will help the company achieve long-term growth and establish a strong position in the retail market.

8. Suggestions

- Kottha's Foods should improve customer service by training staff and responding quickly to customers.
- The company should maintain high quality and freshness of its masala and pickle products.
- It should provide discounts and special offers during festivals to attract customers.
- The company should introduce loyalty programs to encourage repeat purchases

9. Conclusion

The study on customer retention at Kottha's Foods, Kadapa, shows that product quality, pricing, and customer service are

References

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